

TABLE I--ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			M	N	S/P
[Cu(SSCZ)(H ₂ O)]	Green	215	24.01 (24.57)	16.01 (16.63)	—
[Cu(SSCZ)(tn)]	Leaf green	220	19.75 (20.07)	21.84 (22.11)	9.72 (10.10)
[Cu(SSCZ)(<i>r</i> -pic)]	Light green	230	18.61 (19.40)	16.24 (16.78)	—
[Cu(SSCZ)(iq)]	Parrot green	210	16.74 (17.19)	14.62 (15.15)	—
[Cu(SSCZ)(pyNO)]	Yellowish green	250	18.21 (18.94)	16.32 (16.69)	—
[Cu(SSCZ)(Ph ₃ p)]	Dark green	210	12.03 (12.64)	7.74 (8.36)	7.32 (7.70)
[Cd(SSCZ)(H ₂ O)]	White	210	30.01 (30.56)	13.22 (13.66)	—
[Cd(SSCZ)(tn)]	Yellowish white	215	30.14 (30.76)	18.62 (19.16)	8.32 (8.75)
[Cd(SSCZ)(<i>r</i> -pic)]	Cream white	235	28.84 (29.38)	14.02 (14.64)	—
[Cd(SSCZ)(iq)]	White	220	26.52 (26.86)	12.82 (13.38)	—
[Cd(SSCZ)(pyNO)]	White	235	28.62 (29.24)	14.02 (14.57)	—
[Cd(SSCZ)(Ph ₃ p)]	Pale yellow	230	19.74 (20.38)	7.12 (7.62)	5.12 (5.62)

shifted to 1 210 cm⁻¹ when it is bonded to metal through oxygen atom. This shifting to lower frequency could be attributed to change in the N—O bond order as a result of coordination of the ligand through its oxygen atom^{10,11}. In the triphenylphosphine complex strong and sharp bands were observed at 1 480, 1 440 and 1 095 cm⁻¹ due to coordinated ligand of the complexes¹². Some new bands which appeared around 520–510 and 420–410 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of the complexes were due to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} respectively^{13,14}.

Nmr spectra: ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆) of the ligand SSCZ showed characteristic signals at δ 8.48 for CH=N proton, 7.82 for NH proton and around 5.85 for phenolic proton. In the spectrum of [Cu(SSCZ)H₂O] the signal due to CH=N proton showed downfield shift to δ 8.8 indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen. The disappearance of signals due to NH proton suggested¹⁵ the removal of this proton via enolization. Further, the disappearance of signals due to phenolic proton, NH protons indicated dinegative (OON) tridentate chelation by the ligand.

The electronic spectra of the copper(II) complexes showed three bands at 15 500, 19 500 and 22 000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ²B_{1g}→³A_{1g}, ²B_{1g}→²E_g transitions and charge transfer respectively, which indicated square-planar stereochemistry for copper(II)¹⁶.

Acknowledgement

One of the author (R.K.D.) is grateful to the Management of Rourkela Steel Plant for facilities.

References

1. B. BEECROFT, M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GRZEŠKOWIAK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 55.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1969.

3. R. N. PATHAK and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **65**, 119.
4. B. SINGH and H. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 840.
5. A. SYAMAL and K. S. KALE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 46.
6. M. R. PATEL, M. M. PATEL and R. P. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **17**, 415.
7. S. MISHRA and K. M. PUROHIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **64**, 588.
8. M. D. SARDARHASSAIN, S. C. CHAKRABORTY, G. L. TAMBE and A. S. R. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1966, **25**, 737.
9. A. K. DAS and D. V. R. RAO, *Chem. Ind (London)*, 1973, 186.
10. I. S. AHUJA and R. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 561.
11. J. V. QUAGLINO, F. FUJITA, G. FRANZ, D. T. PHILLIPS and S. V. TYREE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3770.
12. G. B. DEACON and S. H. J. GREEN, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1963, **24**, 345.
13. N. C. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 839.
14. D. V. R. RAO and B. PRADHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 733.
15. N. K. SINGH, N. AGARAWAL and R. C. AGGARWAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 1011.
16. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 316.

Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Complexes of *N*-Phenyl-*N'*-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl Thiocarbamide

K. J. SHAH*, B. V. RATHOD and A. D. NAKRANI

University Department of Chemistry,
Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

Manuscript received 21 April 1989, revised 30 July 1990,
accepted 24 September 1990

WE describe herein the synthesis of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes with *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide (1), and their charac-

terisation by spectral, magnetic and conductance data.

Experimental

The ligand *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide was prepared by following the reported procedure¹.

Preparation of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes: An aqueous solution of the metal acetate (0.05 mol) and solution of the ligand (0.1 mol) in DMF were mixed in the presence of the acetate buffer (pH=6.5) and then digested on a water-bath for 1 h. The resulting solids were washed with water, dried under reduced pressure and kept at room temperature (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	Metal	C	H	N
Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₂) ₂	9.05 (9.04)	51.00 (51.60)	3.65 (4.30)	12.02 (12.04)
Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₂) ₂	8.20 (8.47)	52.32 (51.57)	4.17 (4.33)	12.00 (12.12)
Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS ₂) ₂	8.15 (8.50)	52.00 (51.95)	4.25 (4.32)	12.05 (12.12)

*C₁₈H₁₆N₂OS₂ = *N*-Phenyl-*N'*-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide.

Results and Discussion

The low electrical conductivity ($\leq 10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The ir spectra of the ligand showed three bands in the region 1 395–1 595, 1 160–1 420 and 940–1 140 cm^{-1} due to mixed vibrations of thioamide –N–C=S group². A band near 3 150 cm^{-1} is assigned to NH stretching vibration. It also showed sharp bands at 1 635 and 750 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ cyclic and $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ respectively. In the ir spectra of the complexes, –N–C=S bands shifted appreciably to lower frequencies which proved an M–S linkage in the complexes. The lowering in $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cyclic) frequencies in the complexes showed a coordinate link from the nitrogen atom to the metal³. Moreover, a broad band was observed around 3 400 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} in the spectra of the complexes, which was absent in the spectra of the ligand. This band indicates the presence of coordinated water molecule in the complex.

The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} complex (1.92 B.M.) was slightly higher than the spin-only value.

This is attributed to spin-orbit coupling⁴. The Cu^{II} complex gave three bands at 23 800, 19 400 and 15 300 cm^{-1} due to transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ respectively, suggesting a tetragonal geometry⁵.

The Ni^{II} complex gave three bands at 8 680, 14 150 and 23 640 cm^{-1} due to transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively, indicating an octahedral geometry⁶. This is further supported by the magnetic moment value (3.18 B.M.).

10Dq, B and β values were 8 630 cm^{-1} , 785 cm^{-1} and 0.72 respectively. The values of the Racah parameter (B) was found less than the free-ion value (1 040 cm^{-1}) from which $B/B' = \beta$ was calculated, indicating considerable covalent character in the metal-ligand bond⁷. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio was found to be 1.62–1.75. Lowering of this value from 1.8 suggests distorted octahedral nature of the complex. The 10Dq value of the Ni^{II} complex corresponds to a weak ligand field.

Electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex showed three bands at 9 000, 19 000 and 21 090 cm^{-1} due to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ respectively. 10Dq, B and β values were 10 170 cm^{-1} , 885 cm^{-1} and 0.79 respectively. The value of the Racah parameter (B) was less than the free-ion value (1 120 cm^{-1}), and the value of β indicates considerable covalent character in the metal-ligand bond. The ν_3/ν_1 ratio was found to be in the range 2.226–2.414 and lowering of the value suggests distorted octahedral nature of the complex⁸. The 10Dq value of the Co^{II} complex corresponds to a weak ligand field. This is supported by the magnetic moment value (4.32 B.M.).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. N. Misra, Head of the Chemistry Department, Bhavnagar University, for facilities and to Prof. M. M. Taqui Khan, Director, C.S.M.C.R.I., Bhavnagar, for the spectral and magnetic data.

References

1. P. BHARGAVA and S. SHARMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1965, **38**, 905.
2. E. SPINNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1237.
3. D. HADZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2725.
4. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1960, p. 427.
5. A. SYAMAL and K. S. KALE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 46.
6. N. S. GILL, R. S. NYHOLM, G. A. BARCLAY, T. I. CHRISTIE and P. J. PAULING, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 88.
7. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1984, p. 507.
8. B. N. FIGGIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 338.